

The Generalized Fermat Equation and An Elementary Proving

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Abstract

We will propose a new approach to a generalization of Fermat equation. We use a simple method for the proof and investigate the problem using only arithmetic.

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1. Introduction

The generalization of Fermat's Last Theorem has the form.

$$(1.1) \quad A^x + B^y = C^z.$$

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In 1993, Mr Andrew Beal stated a conjecture from the above equation.

The Beal Conjecture [3]

Let $A, B, C, x, y,$ and z be positive integers with $x, y, z > 2$. If $A^x + B^y = C^z$, then $A, B,$ and C have a common prime factor.

There were some published results by Darmon and Granville [1], Bennett, Chen, Dahmen and Yazdani [2], the authors investigated integer solutions of the generalized Fermat equation. Now, we are going to introduce a new and simple approach to solving the conjecture. Two main cases to be solved: If the Eq. 1.1 has a solution, we find a common factor and show that Eq. 1.1 has no solution if the $A, B,$ and C have the greatest common divisor equal to 1.

1.1. *Notations.*

$\mathbb{N} :=$ the set of natural numbers = $\{ 1, 2, 3, \dots \}$

$\mathbb{Z} :=$ the set of integers = $\{ \dots, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, \dots \}$

GCD : Greatest common divisor.

FLT : Fermat's Last Theorem.

Eq. : Equation.

Binomial coefficient: $\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$

$Exp_1 = A^{z-1} - A^{z-2}B + \dots + -AB^{z-2} + B^{z-1}.$

$Sum_p = A^{z-1} + A^{z-2}B + \dots + AB^{z-2} + B^{z-1}.$

1.2. *Organization of the paper.*

In Section 2, we present the basic theory and some lemmas on which our proof is based. We prove the conjecture in Sections 3 and 4. In Section 3, assuming that the conjecture is true, we try to find out a common factor. Otherwise, we will show in Section 4 that Eq. 1.1 has no solution if the A, B and C are pairwise relatively prime. Section 5 is the conclusion.

2. Background theory

We need to prove some basic problems before we can begin to solve the conjecture.

Definition 2.1 (Relatively prime). The integers a and b are called coprime or relatively prime if $\gcd(a, b) = 1$.

THEOREM 2.1. [5, 4] *Let a, b, c be integers.*

- (1) *If $b \mid ac$ and a is relatively prime to b , then $b \mid c$.*
- (2) *If $a \mid c, b \mid c$ and a is relatively prime to b , then $ab \mid c$.*

THEOREM 2.2. [6, 4] *Let $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then*

$$\gcd(a, b) = \gcd(b, a) = \gcd(a, b \pm a).$$

Proof. We only prove that $\gcd(a, b) = \gcd(a, a + b)$, since the other cases can be proved in a similar way. Let $d_1 = \gcd(a, b)$ and $d_2 = \gcd(a, a + b)$. Since $d_1 \mid a$ and $d_1 \mid b$, we have $d_1 \mid (a + b)$, so d_1 is a common divisor of a and $a + b$. It follows that

$$(2.1) \quad d_1 \leq d_2.$$

Similarly, d_2 is a divisor of a and $a + b$ and therefore a and $b = (a + b) - a$. We get

$$(2.2) \quad d_2 \leq d_1.$$

Combine 2.1 and 2.2, we have that $d_2 = d_1$ or $\gcd(a, b) = \gcd(a, a + b)$. \square

LEMMA 2.3 (Bezout's Lemma). [4, 7] *The greatest common divisor of two numbers is a linear combination of them: for all integers a and b there exist $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $\gcd(a, b) = ma + nb$.*

COROLLARY 2.4. *The integers a and b are relatively prime if and only if $ms + nb = 1$ for some $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$.*

LEMMA 2.5. *Let a, b, c be integers, no two of which are zero. Then*

$$\gcd(a, b, c) = \gcd(\gcd(a, b), c).$$

Proof. Let $d = \gcd(a, b, c)$ and $k = \gcd(\gcd(a, b), c)$.

Note that both d and k are positive integers.

We have $k \mid \gcd(a, b)$, $k \mid c$, which implies $k \mid b$, $k \mid a$ and $k \mid c$. We deduce that $k \mid d$, implies that

$$(2.3) \quad k \leq d.$$

On the other hand, since $d = \gcd(a, b, c)$, we get

$$d \mid a, d \mid b \text{ and } d \mid c,$$

implies that $d \mid \gcd(a, b)$ and $d \mid c$ (d is a common divisor of $\gcd(a, b), c$).

Therefore $d \mid k$, deduces that

$$(2.4) \quad d \leq k.$$

Combining 2.3 and 2.4, we conclude that $d = k$. \square

LEMMA 2.6. *Let a, b, c be integers. If $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ and $\gcd(a, c) = 1$, then $\gcd(a, bc) = 1$.*

Proof. Since $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. By Bezout's Lemma, there exist $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that

$$(2.5) \quad ma + nb = 1.$$

Similarly, we have $\gcd(a, c) = 1$, there are also m_1, n_1 such that

$$(2.6) \quad m_1 a + n_1 b = 1.$$

Multiplying 2.5 and 2.6 side by side gives

$$(2.7) \quad a(mm_1 a + nbm_1 + mn_1 c) + bc(nn_1) = 1.$$

By Corollary 2.4, we obtain a, bc are relatively prime or $\gcd(a, bc) = 1$. \square

LEMMA 2.7. *Let a, b, m and n be positive integers. If $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, then $\gcd(a^m, b^n) = 1$.*

Proof. Use mathematical induction to prove this.

We show that $\gcd(a, b^n) = 1$ by induction on n .

- With $n = 2$, we have $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. By Lemma 2.6 we obtain

$$\gcd(a, b \cdot b) = \gcd(a, b^2) = 1.$$

- Assuming $n = k$ holds: $\gcd(a, b^k) = 1$.
- When $n = k + 1$, since $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ and $\gcd(a, b^k) = 1$. We apply Lemma 2.6 again to get $\gcd(a, b \cdot b^k) = \gcd(a, b^{k+1}) = 1$.

By the principal of mathematical induction, we obtain $\gcd(a, b^n) = 1$ for all $n \geq 1$.

Similarly, we have $\gcd(a^m, b^n) = 1$ by using induction on m . \square

LEMMA 2.8. *Let a, b, d be integers. If $d \mid a$ and $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, then $\gcd(d, b) = 1$.*

Proof. Using disproof, suppose that $\gcd(d, b) > 1$. Let $d_0 = \gcd(d, b)$. This means that $d_0 \mid b$, and $d_0 \mid d \mid a$. Which implies that d_0 is a common divisor of a and b . Hence $\gcd(a, b) \geq d_0 > 1$, a contradiction (since $\gcd(a, b) = 1$). Therefore $\gcd(d, b) = 1$. \square

THEOREM 2.9 (Fermat's Last Theorem: FLT).

There are no three positive integers a, b , and c that satisfy the equation

$$a^n + b^n = c^n$$

for any integer value of n greater than 2.

Proof. Please see [8]. \square

LEMMA 2.10. *Let d, B, z and y be positive integers. If $d^z \mid B^y$ and $d > 1$, then $\gcd(d, B) > 1$.*

Proof. Assume $\gcd(d, B) = 1$. By Lemma 2.7, we have

$$\gcd(d, B^y) = 1.$$

In addition, the assumption $d^z \mid B^y$, implies that $d \mid B^y$. So d is a common divisor of d and B^y . So, $\gcd(d, B^y) \geq d$, which means $1 \geq d$, a contradiction

(by assuming $d > 1$).

Thus, we conclude that $\gcd(d, B) > 1$. □

THEOREM 2.11. *If $n \mid A(n)$ and $n \mid (A(n) + B(n))$, then $n \mid B(n)$*

Proof. Note that $A(n)$ is an expression.

Since $n \mid A(n)$, there exists $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $A(n) = mn$.

And $n \mid (A(n) + B(n))$, implies that $(A(n) + B(n)) = kn$ for some $k \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Now, $B(n)$ is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} B(n) &= A(n) + B(n) - A(n) \\ B(n) &= kn - mn = n(k - m). \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, $n \mid B(n)$. □

LEMMA 2.12. *Let A, B, C, x, y, z be positive integers, and $x, y, z \geq 3$.*

- (1) *If $C = 1$, then Eq. 1.1 has no solution.*
- (2) *If $A = 1, B = 1$, then Eq. 1.1 has no solution.*
- (3) *If A, B , and C are relatively prime and $A < C, B < C$, then Eq. 1.1 has no solution if $z \geq x, z \geq y$.*

Proof of 1. Since A and B are positive integers, we deduce that $A \geq 1$ and $B \geq 1$, which implies that $A^x + B^y \geq 2$. If $C = 1$, then $A^x + B^y = C^z = 1$, this is absurd. Thus, Eq. 1.1 has no solution. □

Proof of 2. The assumption $A = 1, B = 1$. Now, Eq. 1.1 can be written

$$(2.8) \quad \begin{aligned} 1^x + 1^y &= C^z \\ 2 &= C^z. \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, $C \mid 2$. Which implies $C = 1$ or $C = 2$.

If $C = 1$, then Eq. 1.1 has no solution (by proof of 1).

If $C = 2$, then Eq. 1.1 is rewritten

$$(2.9) \quad 1^x + 1^y = 2 = 2^z.$$

It follows that $z = 1$, which doesn't satisfy the condition $z > 2$.

Therefore, Eq. 1.1 also has no solution. □

Proof of 3. Assume $A^x + B^y = C^z$ has a solution. Because FLT, if $y = z$, then $x < z$ or if $x = z$, then $y < z$.

Without loss of generality, we can suppose $A < B$. Since $B < C$, then $B \leq C - 1$, and $A \leq C - 2$. Therefore, we deduce that

$$(2.10) \quad B^y \leq B^z \leq (C - 1)^z,$$

$$(2.11) \quad A^x \leq A^{z-1} \leq (C - 2)^{z-1}.$$

Or

$$(2.12) \quad B^y \leq B^{z-1} \leq (C-1)^{z-1},$$

$$(2.13) \quad A^x \leq A^z \leq (C-2)^z.$$

Adding 2.10 and 2.11 to get

$$(2.14) \quad A^x + B^y \leq (C-2)^{z-1} + (C-1)^z$$

$$(2.15) \quad C^z \leq (C-2)^{z-1} + (C-1)^z$$

However, we have

$$(2.16) \quad \begin{aligned} (C-2)^{z-1} + (C-1)^z &= (C-2)^{z-1} + (C-1)(C-1)^{z-1} < C^{z-1} + (C-1)C^{z-1} \\ &= (C-2)^{z-1} + (C-1)(C-1)^{z-1} < C^z. \end{aligned} \quad \blacksquare$$

Which would contradict 2.15.

Other case, adding 2.12 and 2.13 to get

$$(2.17) \quad A^x + B^y \leq (C-2)^z + (C-1)^{z-1}$$

$$(2.18) \quad C^z \leq (C-2)^z + (C-1)^{z-1}.$$

Similarly, we obtain that

$$(2.19) \quad \begin{aligned} (C-2)^z + (C-1)^{z-1} &= (C-2)(C-2)^{z-1} + (C-1)^{z-1} < (C-1)(C)^{z-1} + (C)^{z-1} \\ &= (C-2)(C-2)^{z-1} + (C-1)^{z-1} < C^z, \end{aligned} \quad \blacksquare$$

contradicting Eq. 2.18.

Therefore, we conclude that Eq. 1.1 has no solution. \square

LEMMA 2.13. *Let h, k, z be integers and h, k are non-zero, $h^z = k^z$ where $z > 1$ and $\gcd(h, k) = 1$.*

- (1) *If h, k are positive integers, then $h = k = 1$.*
- (2) *If z is odd and $h \geq 1$, then $h = k = 1$.*
- (3) *If z is even and $h \geq 1$, then $k = \pm 1$.*

Proof of 1. Since $h, k > 0$ and $h^z = k^z$, implies that $h = k$. If $h > 1$, then $\gcd(h, k) = \gcd(h, h) = h > 1$, contradicting. Therefore, $h = k = 1$. \square

Proof of 2. The assumption Eq. $h^z = k^z$, implies that $h = k$. If $h > 1$, then $\gcd(h, k) = \gcd(h, h) = h > 1$, contradicting. Therefore, $h = k = 1$. \square

Proof of 3. Similarly, we obtain $h = k$. If $h > 1$, then $\gcd(h, k) = \gcd(h, h) = h > 1$, a contradiction. Hence $1 = k^z$, which deduces $k = \pm 1$. \square

3. The proof that A , B and C has a common factor

Let p , q be integers, there are two cases for the greatest common divisor of them:

- $\gcd(p, q) > 1$.
- $\gcd(p, q) = 1$ (*coprime*).

Assuming that Eq. 1.1 has a solution, we try to find a common factor of A , B and C by considering the GCD of the positive integers A , B and C .

3.1. Examination of $\gcd(A, C)$.

Proof. There are two cases to consider: $\gcd(A, C) > 1$ and $\gcd(A, C) = 1$.

Case 1: Assume $\gcd(A, C) = d > 1$

Since $\gcd(A, C) = d$, there exist $k, t \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$(3.1) \quad A = kd,$$

$$(3.2) \quad C = td.$$

Equation 1.1 deduces that $B^y = C^z - A^x$, or equivalently

$$(3.3) \quad B^y = (td)^z - (kd)^x = d^3(t^z d^{z-3} - k^z d^{y-3}).$$

Clearly, $d^3 \mid B^y$ and $d > 1$. By Lemma 2.10, we obtain $\gcd(d, B) = d_0 > 1$, $d_0 \in \mathbb{N}$. Hence $d_0 \mid B$, $d_0 \mid d \mid A$, and $d_0 \mid d \mid C$. So d_0 is a common divisor of A , B , C .

Furthermore, by Lemma 2.5, we have $\gcd(A, B, C) = \gcd(\gcd(A, C), B) = \gcd(d, B) = d_0$. \square

EXAMPLE 3.1. Let $A = 456$, $C = 152$, $x = 3$, $z = 4$, we get $\gcd(456, 152) = \gcd(152 \cdot 3, 152) = 152 = d$.

$$(3.4) \quad B^y = 152^4 - 456^3 = 152^3(152 - 27) = 760^3.$$

Therefore, we obtain $B = 760$, $y = 3$, and $d_0 = \gcd(A, B, C) = 152$. $d_0 = 152 = 2^3 \cdot 19$, d_0 is a common factor of A , B , C .

Otherwise, if $\gcd(A, C) = 1$, then what happens? please go to the next subsection.

b) Assume $\gcd(A, C) = 1$. We need to consider $\gcd(A, B)$ or $\gcd(B, C)$, there are two cases to examine.

- (1) If $\gcd(A, B) = d_a > 1$ or $\gcd(B, C) = d_b > 1$.
- (2) If $\gcd(A, B) = 1$ and $\gcd(B, C) = 1$.

Proof of 1. If $\gcd(A, B) = d_a$, then there exist $k, t \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$(3.5) \quad A = kd_a.$$

$$(3.6) \quad B = td_a.$$

Equation 1.1 can be written $(kd_a)^x + (td_a)^y = C^z$, or equivalently

$$(3.7) \quad d_a^3(t^x d_a^{x-3} + k^y d^{y-3}) = C^z.$$

Obviously, $d_a^3 \mid C^z$ and $d_a > 1$. By Lemma 2.10, we get

$$\gcd(d_a, C) = d_0 > 1.$$

Hence $d_0 \mid C, d_0 \mid d_a \mid A$ and $d_0 \mid d_a \mid B$.

Moreover, by Lemma 2.5, we get $\gcd(A, B, C) = \gcd(\gcd(A, C), B) = \gcd(1, B) = 1$. We know that $d_0 \leq \gcd(A, B, C) = 1$, a contradiction (since $d_0 > 1$).

The proof that if $\gcd(B, C) = d_b$ is similar. Hence, we also get the contradiction if Eq. 1.1 has a solution.

Therefore, in this case, Eq. 1.1 has no solution. \square

Proof of 2. Suppose $\gcd(A, B) = 1$, $\gcd(B, C) = 1$ and $\gcd(A, C) = 1$. Please see a later proof. As a special case, if A, B, C are pairwise relatively prime. \square

3.2. Examination of $\gcd(A, B)$.

There are also two cases to consider:

Proof. We will consider two cases:

- (1) If $\gcd(A, B) > 1$.
- (2) If $\gcd(A, B) = 1$.

The proof is similar to 3.1. \square

3.3. Examination of $\gcd(B, C)$.

The proof is also similar to 3.1.

Remark 3.1. Let $d_1 = \gcd(A, B)$, $d_2 = \gcd(A, C)$, and $d_3 = \gcd(B, C)$. If $d_i = 1$ and $d_j > 1$ where $i \neq j$, $1 \leq i, j \leq 3$, then Eq. 1.1 has no solution.

Having considered three parts: 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3, we conclude that if Eq. 1.1 is solved, then there exists $d_0 = \gcd(A, B, C) > 1$. In other words, A, B and C have a common factor.

Otherwise, is there a (A, B, C, x, y, z) ? that satisfies Beal Conjecture if A, B, C are pairwise relatively prime. This is the last case.

Now, we will present the *special case* in the next section.

4. The proof that Eq. 1.1 has no solution for the special case

The special case is: A, B and C are pairwise relatively prime.
(see next version).

5. Conclusion

Assuming that $A^x + B^y = C^z$ then we have found a common factor of A , B , and C in Section 3, the common factor is $\gcd(A, B, C) > 1$.

Otherwise, we proved that Eq. 1.1 has no solution.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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